

Mercury exposure triggers diabetes mellitus through a pancreatic beta cell endoplasmic reticulum stress mechanism

La exposición al mercurio desencadena la diabetes mellitus a través de un mecanismo de estrés del retículo endoplásmico de las células beta pancreáticas.

319

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Abstract

Mercury the source of free radicals, can trigger the activation of ER stress can cause beta cell pancreas injuries and result in diabetes mellitus. There have been many studies on mercury toxicity in various organs, but there are still few scientific studies that examine the pathomechanism of diabetes mellitus caused by mercury through the endoplasmic reticulum stress. This study was conducted to investigate the triggering of the endoplasmic reticulum stress pathway due to mercury exposure in beta cell pancreas injury resulting diabetes mellitus. Research using randomized true laboratory experiment method with post-test control group design. The number of samples used was 28 Wistar rats. The research group consisted of 2 groups, control group was given aquadest ad libitum, and intervention group was given water contaminated with mercury per oral once a

day (15 kg/WB). The treatment period was 14 consecutive days and on the 15th day, blood samples were taken. ER stress marker was assessed by examining Ca²⁺ count, expression levels of GRP 78 and JNKp; beta cell injuries were assessed by examining fasting blood sugar. The collected data were analyzed by independent t-test with 95% confidence level; significant if p>0.05. The study found that mercury exposure can trigger ER stress activation of pancreatic beta cells and cause impairment in their function in metabolising glucose, resulting in hyperglycaemia, which can lead to diabetes mellitus. Further research needs to be conducted to look for the involvement of higher-level cellular biomolecular mechanisms that could form the basis of specific therapies for mercury-induced diabetes mellitus.

Keywords: ER stress, Ca²⁺ intracellular, GRP78, JNKp, Mercury, Beta cells pancreas

El mercurio la fuente de radicales libres puede desencadenar la activación del estrés del retículo endoplásmico puede causar lesiones en las células beta del páncreas y la diabetes mellitus resultante. Se han realizado muchos estudios sobre la toxicidad del mercurio en diversos órganos, pero todavía hay pocos estudios científicos que examinen el patomecanismo de la diabetes mellitus causada por el mercurio a través del estrés del retículo endoplásmico. Este estudio se llevó a cabo para investigar la activación de la vía del estrés del retículo endoplásmico debido a la exposición al mercurio en la lesión de la célula beta del páncreas resultante de la diabetes mellitus. La investigación utilizó el método de experimento de laboratorio real aleatorizado con diseño de grupo de control posterior a la prueba. El número de muestras utilizadas fue de 28 ratas Wistar. El grupo de investigación consistió en 2 grupos, el grupo de control recibió agua ad libitum, y el grupo de intervención recibió agua contaminada con mercurio por vía oral una vez al día (15 kg/WB). El periodo de tratamiento fue de 14 días consecutivos y el día 15 se tomaron muestras de sangre. Se evaluó el marcador de estrés RE examinando el recuento de Ca^{2+} , los niveles de expresión de GRP78 y JNKp; las lesiones de las células beta se evaluaron examinando la glucemia en ayunas. Los datos recogidos se analizaron mediante una prueba t independiente con un nivel de confianza del 95%; significativa si $p > 0,05$. El estudio reveló que la exposición al mercurio puede desencadenar la activación del estrés de retorno de las células beta pancreáticas y alterar su función de metabolización de la glucosa, lo que provoca hiperglucemia y, por consiguiente, diabetes mellitus. Es necesario seguir investigando para buscar la implicación de mecanismos biomoleculares celulares de nivel superior que podrían constituir la base de terapias específicas para la diabetes mellitus inducida por mercurio.

Palabras clave: Estrés de RE, Ión calcio, GRP78, JNKp, Mercurio, Células beta pancreáticas

Mercury has become a widespread pollutant that causes negative effects on humans, can accumulate, enlarge, and reach high levels in the ecological food chain, and people can consume it through food intake, especially fish and seafood and cause toxic effects¹⁻³longevity in the atmosphere, and ability to accumulate in the human body via bioaccumulation. The pollution of terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems with toxic heavy metals is a major environmental concern that has consequences for public health. Most heavy metals occur naturally, but a few are derived from anthropogenic sources. Heavy metals are characterized by their high atomic mass and toxicity to living organisms. Most heavy metals cause environmental and atmospheric pollution, and may be lethal to humans. Heavy metals can become strongly toxic by mixing with different environmental elements, such as water, soil, and air, and humans and other living organisms can be exposed to them through the food chain. Plenty of experimental studies were performed to appraise the promising treatment options from natural products. Additionally, nanotechnology based treatment options are being constantly developed. As an emerging field, nanotechnology is making substantial advances in the analysis and removal of heavy metals from complicated matrices. Removal of heavy metal has been accomplished by the use of a variety of nanomaterials, including graphene and its derivatives, magnetic nanoparticles, metal oxide nanoparticles, and carbon nanotubes, to name a few. Using nanotechnology for heavy metal analysis and removal from food and water resources provides many benefits over traditional methods. These advantages include a broad linear range, low detection and quantification limits, a high sensitivity, and high selectivity. Therefore this review aimed to explore the environmental consequences of the heavy metals, toxicity to the human health, as well as novel therapeutics development from the natural resources. Additionally, nanotechnological and nanomedicinal applications to treat heavy metal toxicity are also highlighted in this review.

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given": "Abubakr M.", "non-dropping-particle": "", "parse-names": false, "suffix": ""}, {"dropping-particle": "", "family": "Khandaker", "given": "Mayeen Uddin", "non-dropping-particle": "", "parse-names": false, "suffix": ""}, {"dropping-particle": "", "family": "Osman", "given": "Hamid", "non-dropping-particle": "", "parse-names": false, "suffix": ""}, {"dropping-particle": "", "family": "Alhumaydhi", "given": "Fahad A.", "non-dropping-particle": "", "parse-names": false, "suffix": ""}, {"dropping-particle": "", "family": "Simalgandara", "given": "Jesus", "non-dropping-particle": "", "parse-names": false, "suffix": ""}], "container-title": "Journal of King Saud University - Science", "id": "ITEM-1", "issue": "3", "issued": {"date-parts": ["2022"]}, "page": "101865", "publisher": "The Author(s). Mercury is part of the group of heavy metals that has the highest toxicity in its class so that even at low concentrations it will cause toxicity to organs in the form of increased blood glucose levels, liver cell damage through increased transaminase enzymes, and increased MDA levels⁴. However, the level of toxicity exhibited by this compound depends on the number and length of time a living organism is exposed to it⁵. Mercury leads to significant changes in the biochemistry of cells. Mercury primarily binds to sulfhydryl groups and secondarily to amide, carboxyl, and phosphoryl groups, which interrupt cellular enzymes and protein systems throughout the body. Therefore, mercury can cause significant dysfunction of enzymes, membranes, transport mechanisms, and structural proteins.⁶ Lead, chromium, cadmium, and arsenic have been the most common heavy metals that induced human poisonings. Here, we reviewed the mechanistic action of these heavy metals according to the available animal and human studies. Acute or chronic poisonings may occur following exposure through water, air, and food. Bioaccumulation of these heavy metals leads to a diversity of toxic effects on a variety of body tissues and organs. Heavy metals disrupt cellular events including growth, proliferation, differentiation, damage-repairing processes, and apoptosis. Comparison of the mechanisms of action reveals similar pathways for these metals to induce toxicity including ROS generation, weakening of the antioxidant defense, enzyme inactivation, and oxidative stress. On the other hand, some of them have selective binding to specific macromolecules. The interaction of lead with aminolevulinic acid dehydratase and ferrochelatase is within this context. Reactions of other heavy metals with certain proteins were discussed as well. Some toxic metals including chromium, cadmium, and arsenic cause genomic instability. Defects in DNA repair following the induction of oxidative stress and DNA damage by the three metals have been considered as the cause of their carcinogenicity. Even with the current knowledge of hazards of heavy metals, the incidence of poisoning remains considerable and requires preventive and effective treatment. The application of chelation therapy for the management of metal poisoning could be another aspect of heavy metals to be reviewed in the future.", "author": [{"dropping-particle": "", "family": "Balali-Mood", "given": "Mahdi", "non-dropping-particle": "", "parse-

names": false, "suffix": ""}, {"dropping-particle": "", "family": "Naseri", "given": "Kobra", "non-dropping-particle": "", "parse-names": false, "suffix": ""}, {"dropping-particle": "", "family": "Tahergorabi", "given": "Zoya", "non-dropping-particle": "", "parse-names": false, "suffix": ""}, {"dropping-particle": "", "family": "Khazdair", "given": "Mohammad Reza", "non-dropping-particle": "", "parse-names": false, "suffix": ""}, {"dropping-particle": "", "family": "Sadeghi", "given": "Mahmood", "non-dropping-particle": "", "parse-names": false, "suffix": ""}], "container-title": "Frontiers in Pharmacology", "id": "ITEM-1", "issue": "April", "issued": {"date-parts": ["2021"]}, "page": "1-19", "title": "Toxic mechanisms of five heavy metals: mercury, lead, chromium, cadmium, and arsenic", "type": "article-journal", "volume": "12", "uris": [{"http": "http://www.mendeley.com/documents/?uuid=c5c073fa-455d-4369-984a-46d4f6873398"}], "mendeley": {"formattedCitation": "⁶", "plainTextFormattedCitation": "6", "previouslyFormattedCitation": "⁶", "properties": {"noteIndex": 0}, "schema": "https://github.com/citation-style-language/schema/raw/master/csl-citation.json"} Its effects are mainly associated with oxidative stress production of reactive oxygen species, depletion of glutathione (GSH), and alteration of protein synthesis⁷.

Mercury causes pancreatic beta cell defects cause abnormalities in insulin secretion as the basis of diabetes pathophysiology is very closely related to apoptosis and necrosis through oxidative stress pathways^{8,9}. This mechanism of cell death involves intrinsic pathways in the endoplasmic reticulum through the endoplasmic reticulum stress, which will activate apoptosis, necrosis and inflammatory signals^{10,11}. The role of RE in pancreatic beta cells as intracellular Ca²⁺ stores not only regulates cytosolic Ca²⁺ signaling but also conforms newly synthesized protein folds. Changes in ER homeostasis such as intracellular Ca²⁺ depletion and defects in protein fold conformations are early events in the pathophysiology of many diseases. Loss of Ca²⁺ in the lumen causes defects in insulin secretion through the process of insulin exocytosis of cell membranes also aggravates the state of incorrect protein conformation. Biological systems already provide adaptive mechanisms for ER stress conditions that aim to restore ER function to normal or result in cell death^{8,12} and ER stress can lead to ER Ca²⁺ reduction, beta-cell dysfunction, and an increased risk of type 2 diabetes. However, the mechanistic effects of ER stress on individual calcium channels are not well understood. To determine the effects of tunicamycin-induced ER stress on ER inositol 1,4,5-triphosphate receptors (IP3Rs)¹³. Failure of the homeostatic mechanism of RE will trigger a decrease in intracellular Ca²⁺ will also trigger a disruption in protein conformation that will activate the *unfolded protein response* (UPR) mechanism, which functions to restore normal ER function or eliminate damaged cells^{10,14-16} however, leads to the generation of free radicals, and thus can lead to oxidative stress and potentially to age-related cognitive decay and even neurodegenerative diseases. The regulation of this system requires

a complex monitoring network to maintain proper oxygen homeostasis. Furthermore, the high content of mitochondria in the brain has elevated glucose demands, and thus requires a normal redox balance. Maintaining this is mediated by adaptive stress response pathways that permit cells to survive oxidative stress and to minimize cellular damage. These stress pathways rely on the proper function of the endoplasmic reticulum (ER). In diabetes mellitus, an increase in glucose is associated with an increase in the production of ROS, which leads to an increase in oxidative stress¹⁷ which significantly worsens the prognosis and quality of life of patients. Prevention of cardiovascular complications in patients with diabetes includes a set of measures aimed at reducing blood glucose levels, normalising blood pressure, improving lipid metabolism and preventing microvascular disorders. Important aspects are early diagnosis, regular health monitoring, and the use of pharmacotherapy such as angiotensin-converting enzyme (ACE).¹⁸ Inorganic mercury targets its action on pancreatic beta cells and causes dysfunction and apoptosis by several mechanisms such as alteration of Ca²⁺ homeostasis, activation of PI3K signaling pathway, MAPK, Akt, and ROS production^{19,20}.

There are still few studies that explain in depth the occurrence of ER stress triggered due to mercury exposure, which causes pancreatic beta cell defects through endoplasmic reticulum stress which will result in hyperglycemic conditions that will lead to diabetes mellitus. Therefore, it is very necessary to study to further explore this to find the pathophysiology of diabetes mellitus due to mercury exposure and it is hoped that this discovery will be one of the first step to find the right therapy based on the pathophysiology.

The study was authorized by the local Health Research Ethics Committee of Faculty of Medicine and Health Science, Lambung Mangkurat University, South Kalimantan, Indonesia No: 042/KEPK-FKIK/EC/2024. Research using true laboratory experiment method with a random design complete with a post-test one group with control group design..

The study subjects consist of 28 male Wistar strain *Rattus Norvegicus* rats sourced from the Animal Laboratory of the Faculty of Medicine, Brawijaya University, East Java, Indonesia. The rats are aged 8 to 12 weeks, weigh between 200- 250 g. The expression of GRP78, JNKp, and Ca²⁺ measured using immunofluorescence examination with JNKp (MKK Ser271+Thr275 Antibody, PerCP-Cy7 Cobjugated, cat No. bs-3277R-Per-Cy, BIOSS®), GRP78 (GRP78 Polyclonal Antibody, Cy5.5 Conjugated-100, cat No bs-1219R-Cy 5.5, BIOSS®), dan Ca²⁺ (Fura-2, Pentapotassium salt, cell impermeant 1 mg, cat No F1200, INVITROGEN®). The manufacturer's guidelines were meticulously adhered to during the testing procedure. The reagents, standard solutions, and samples were prepared and analyzed at room temperature.

Acclimatization stage

The Wistar strain *Rattus norvegicus* underwent a one-week acclimatization period in cages of 40 cm x 60 cm x 60 cm within a controlled animal laboratory, where the temperature was maintained at 20°C–22°C, humidity at 50%–60%, and a 12-hour light-dark cycle was implemented. Standard commercial rodent pellets and water were provided to the rats on an *ad libitum* basis. The study began with experimental rats being acclimatized for one week in separate cages to provide the same physical and psychological conditions. The rats received their normal diet, and daily behavioral and physical observations will be conducted to track any changes in each rat. The acclimatization stage ended on day eight. The exclusion criteria of this study was rats that die during the acclimatization phase and HgCl₂ induction process or look sick after 3 days induction.

Intervention and termination stage

The research procedure included establishing the requisite equipment and techniques, along with selecting research objects and subjects that met the inclusion requirements. Total of 28 male adult Wistar rats were randomly assigned to 2 groups. Research group was divided into 2 groups: the control group (ctrl) rats were given distilled water and the intervention group (Hg) were given water contaminated with HgCl₂ per oral once a day (15 kg/WB) for 14 days. The administration was carried via the oral route. Feed and water was given *ad libitum*.

Immunofluorescence examination procedure

Grow cells on sterile 12 mm glass coverslips placed in 24-well culture plates. Remove culture medium (step 2). Gently wash cells 3 times with ice-cold PBS for 5 minutes per wash. Fix cells by adding a volume of 1% formaldehyde in PBS equal to the original volume of culture medium. Incubate on ice for 5 minutes. Remove the fixative and wash as in Step 2. Permeabilize cells for 20 minutes on ice with permeabilization buffer. Prepare primary antibody appropriately diluted in antibody dilution buffer. React cells with primary antibody for 1 hour at room temperature. Wash as in Step 2. Prepare dilution of fluorescein-conjugated affinity-purified secondary antibody. React cells for 1 hour at room temperature with reagent. Alternatively, use a biotin-conjugated secondary antibody followed by a wash as in Step 2. Add fluorescein-conjugated diluted 1:200 in PBS buffer. React for 30 minutes at room temperature. Wash as in Step 2. Counterstain cells with bis-benzimide solution for 15 minutes at room temperature. Wash as in Step 2. Add aqueous mounting agent. Affix coverslips to slides. Allow coverslips to dry in the dark before viewing.

Statistical analysis

Data analysis using the Shapiro-Wilk test was implemented to determine normality, and Levene's test was implemented to determine homogeneity. The data were normally distributed and homogeneous ($p > 0.05$). Statistical analyses were conducted using SPSS software version 25. All variables analysis (FBG level, GRP78, Ca^{2+} , and JNKp expressions) by the independent t test to compared between intervention and control group. The data was analyzed with t test independent with significant value $P < 0.05$. The confidence level used in the study was 95%, and the significance level value $p < 0.05$.

Results

The table shows the results of the evaluation of variables measured by an independent t-test which is used to compare the results of the control group research to the treatment group.

Table 1. Effects of Mercury Exposure on FBG, GRP78, JNKp, and Ca^{2+} intracellular

Variables	Control	Intervention (HgCl ₂)	P value
FBG (mg/dl)	90.00±10.43	129.07±10.455	0.005*
GRP78(intensitas/mm ²)	740.82±389.037	2234.30±21.14	0.000*
JNKp(intensitas/mm ²)	359.859±80.314	2319.01±1317.66	0.003*
Ca^{2+} (intensitas/mm ²)	2385.369±480.68	1088,796±127.74	0.004*

* $P < 0.05$ (significantly compared with the control group) ; independent t-tests

Figure 2. Immunofluorescence showed the expression of GRP 78 (red) and JNKp (yellow); A = control group and B = HgCl₂ intervention group

Figure 3. Immunofluorescence showed the expression of intracellular Ca^{2+} ions (green), counterstain (red) ; A = control group and B = HgCl₂ intervention group

Mercury acts on the active side of protein enzymes in the sulfhydryl group of cysteine residues and bonds covalently to metals. The high affinity of mercury for the sulfhydryl group of the enzyme catalytic site is the main commonly known way of inactivating enzymes⁶lead, chromium, cadmium, and arsenic have been the most common heavy metals that induced human poisonings. Here, we reviewed the mechanistic action of these heavy metals according to the available animal and human studies. Acute or chronic poisonings may occur following exposure through water, air, and food. Bioaccumulation of these heavy metals leads to a diversity of toxic effects on a variety of body tissues and organs. Heavy metals disrupt cellular events including growth, proliferation, differentiation, damage-repairing processes, and apoptosis. Comparison of the mechanisms of action reveals similar pathways for these metals to induce toxicity including ROS generation, weakening of the antioxidant defense, enzyme inactivation, and oxidative stress. On the other hand, some of them have selective binding to specific macromolecules. The interaction of lead with aminolevulinic acid dehydratase and ferrochelatase is within this context. Reactions of other heavy metals with certain proteins were discussed as well. Some toxic metals including chromium, cadmium, and arsenic cause genomic instability. Defects in DNA repair following the induction of oxidative stress and DNA damage by the three metals have been considered as the cause of their carcinogenicity. Even with the current knowledge of hazards of heavy metals, the incidence of poisoning remains considerable and requires preventive and effective treatment. The application of chelation therapy for the management of metal poisoning could be another aspect of heavy metals to be reviewed in the future.

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p>,"plainTextFormattedCitation": "6", "previouslyFormattedCitation": "⁶"; "properties": {"noteIndex": 0}, "schema": "https://github.com/citation-style-language/schema/raw/master/csl-citation.json". Mercury releases radical oxygen during decomposition and the release of ROS causes severe damage to the cell by activating the peroxidized lipid chain of the cell membrane. When mercury circulates in the body, disulfides will be produced which by strongly binding to other protein sulfide groups thereby changing protein structure and enzyme function. Mercury can affect gene expression, disregulate metabolism, and/or interfere with signal transduction, including phosphorylation of p38MAPK^{5,10,20,21}a long-lasting organic pollutant, is known to induce cytotoxic effects in mammalian cells. Epidemiological studies have suggested that environmental exposure to MeHg is linked to the development of diabetes mellitus (DM. Associated with the incidence of diabetes, mercury targets its action on β pancreatic cells and causes dysfunction and apoptosis by several mechanisms such as alteration of Ca^{2+} homeostasis, activation of PI3K, Akt signaling pathway, and the production of ROS^{22,23}their emissions have risen significantly over the last few decades, quickly gaining attention due to their crucial role in the development of several metabolic disorders, notably diabetes mellitus. Cadmium and arsenic not only spread widely in our atmosphere but are also linked to a wide range of health hazards. These are primarily accumulated in the liver, kidney, and pancreas once they reach the human body, where they have deleterious effects on the metabolism of glucose and its association with other metabolic pathways, particularly glycolysis, gluconeogenesis, and gluconeogenesis, by altering and impairing the specific activity of major enzymes. Impairment of hepatic glucose homeostasis plays a crucial role in diabetes mellitus pathogenesis. Impaired liver and kidney functions, as well as decreased pancreatic and muscle function, also contribute significantly to elevated levels of blood glucose. Heavy metals have the potential to cause changes in the conformation in these enzymes. They also impair hormonal balance by destroying the pancreas and adrenal glands. Such metals often facilitate the development of reactive oxygen species and inhibit antioxidant defense mechanisms, with multiple organs subsequently damaged. This review briefly discusses the involvement of heavy metals in metabolic disorders such as diabetes mellitus, the enzymes involved in this pathway, and glucose homeostasis.

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The endoplasmic reticulum is a vast intracellular organelle that provides a place for protein modification and folding. Disturbances in the ectral or intraluminal environment of RE can affect protein folding and processing and vice versa. The reduction of folding capacity and the accumulation of misfolded proteins within the ER activate a series of signaling pathways collectively known as the RE stress response or *unfolded protein response* (UPR). UPR acts to modulate the folding capacity and protein load in the ER to restore homeostasis. UPR signaling should act to improve survival and adaptation to RE stress, but it can also increase cell death in the event of excessive proteotoxic stimuli ^{24,25}including protein folding, lipid synthesis, and calcium homeostasis. The ER homeostasis is maintained by a conserved set of signaling cascades called the Unfolded Protein Response (UPR).

In this study, data were obtained that mercury exposure can trigger ER stress which results in the occurrence of UPR which can be seen from the increased expression of JNKp protein kinase and GRP78 protein conformational companion protein (Table 1 and Figure 2). The results of this study are in line with the research conducted by Placido Rojas-Francoa et al. which showed that HgCl₂ activates PERK, ATF-4, ATF-6, and IRE1²⁶. Likewise, research conducted by Wei Liu et al. found that methylmercury causes oxidative stress, apoptosis, increased expression of GRP78, GRP94, Xbp1, ATF4, ER kinase-eIF2a, inositol, and ATF6, as well as EBP and caspase-12 proteins²⁷which induces severe toxic effects in central nervous system. Oxidative stress is involved in various ways of intracellular physiological or patho-

logical processes including neuronal apoptosis. For understanding the ways that oxidative stress participating in MeHg-induced apoptosis, the current study attempted to explore the effects of oxidative stress on endoplasmic reticulum (ER). The results of this study are in line with the theory of the occurrence of the UPR response, namely the UPR activation process encourages an increase in the expression of companion proteins (GRP 78, Chaperone, calsineurin, calreticulin/calnexin, GRP 94), an increase in protein catabolism through the degradation system associated with RE (ERAD) or imposing a cell death response (macroautophagy) if protein damage is too severe. The presence of these companion proteins is to facilitate the conformation of synthesized proteins. In addition, there are 3 main sensor proteins involved in the detection of RE stress and activating UPR signals in the cytosol and other organelles, namely IRE1, PERK, and ATF6. UPR sensor proteins have their own peculiarities in the activation process. A sensor protein directly related to its activation by p38MAPK that can regulate UPR and cellular response to RE stress is IRE-1²⁸. The IRE1 protein is activated by inflammatory conditions by activating the IRE1-JNKp-ASK axis through binding to the transcription factor TRAF2 (causing the production of inflammatory cytokines and increased immune cells). Other sensor proteins (PERK&ATF6) also contribute to inflammation by activating NF-κB through different mechanisms. Ultimately, if RE stress and UPR activation are chronic, it can lead to oxidative stress and ROS production which further exacerbates necrosis and leads to hyperglycemia ²⁹⁻³².

Another role of RE is to maintain Ca²⁺ homeostasis by strictly regulating the storage and release of Ca²⁺ in the luminal RE to the cytosol. Calcium plays an important role in insulin secretion, acting as the main signaling molecule that triggers the release of insulin from pancreatic beta cells so that if there is a disturbance in its amount in the ER then it impacts the hyperglycemic event. Failure of the homeostatic mechanism of RE, for example, the occurrence of inhibition of SERCA channels, IP channels, and RyR channels will trigger a decrease in intracellular Ca²⁺.^{16,33}

One of the objectives of the study was to find evidence that exposure to mercury can stimulate ER stress which has an impact on intracellular Ca²⁺ homeostasis disorders. In this study, the number of Ca²⁺ RE of pancreatic beta cells was lower in the intervention group compared to the control group (Table 1 and Figure 3). The results of the study of reducing the amount of Ca²⁺ are in line with previous studies that showed exposure to mercury HgCl₂ targets its toxicity to the pancreatic organs by altering the intracellular homeostasis of Ca²⁺ in cells ^{10,34,35}a long-lasting organic pollutant, is known to induce cytotoxic effects in mammalian cells. Epidemiological studies have suggested that environmental exposure to MeHg is linked to the development of diabetes mellitus (DM). A decrease in the number of Ca²⁺ ions is related to the

inhibition of the SERCA channel, IP channel, and RyR channel will trigger a decrease in intracellular Ca^{2+} .^{16,33} In addition, the occurrence of UPR and Ca^{2+} ion defects cause hyperglycemic through the activation of the UPR PERK1 main sensor protein which is related to Ca^{2+} homeostasis and the IRE1 protein which activates the IRE1-JNKp-TRAF2 axis resulting in the disruption of pancreatic beta cell metabolism.^{25,32} a pathway which attempts to restore cellular equilibrium in the face of ER stress. Unremitting ER stress, and insufficient compensation for it results in beta-cell apoptosis, a process that has been linked to both type 1 diabetes (T1D).

Methylmercury toxicity can interfere with the development and function of pancreatic beta cells, resulting in an increase in blood sugar.³⁶ Based on the results of the study, it was found that there was a significant increase in the GDP of the intervention group compared to the control group (Table 1). In rats, there is a classification of GDP levels if a GDP level of >126 mg/dL (7.0 mmol/L) is considered a fasting glucose disorder/prediabetes, while a GDP level of >135 mg/dL (7.5 mmol/L) indicates a condition of diabetes mellitus. Based on the results of GDP in the intervention group (GDP of the intervention group = 129 mg/dl) is included in the classification of fasting glucose disorders/prediabetes. These results are in line with the results of a study conducted by Faheem Maqbul et al. which found that administration of MeHg 2.5 mg, 5 mg and 10 mg for 4 weeks with a dose of 2.5 – 5 mg/kgBB peroral can lead to an increase in GDP levels (dose 2.5 mg; 117 ± 3.1 mg/dL, dose 5 mg; 138.16 ± 6.2 and dose 10 mg; 149.5 ± 6.6)³⁷ various other forms of mercury can enter human body either from environment like inhalation or through dental amalgams. The present study was designed to assess MeHg induced toxicity in mouse plasma and pancreatic islets with respect to insulin secretion, oxidative balance, glucose tolerance, gene expression, caspases 3 and 9 activities. MeHg was dissolved in tap water and administered at doses 2.5, 5 and 10 mg/kg/day, for 4 weeks. In mice, MeHg significantly caused increase in plasma insulin as well as C-peptides. Glucose intolerance, insulin resistance and hyperglycemia are main consequences of our study that correlate with the gene expression changes of glucose homeostasis as well. MeHg caused increase lipid peroxidation in a dose-dependent manner in plasma as well as pancreatic islets. In addition, total thiol molecules and ferrous reducing antioxidant power in MeHg treated group was decreased in plasma as well as pancreatic islets. Caspases 3 and 9 activities of pancreatic islets were upregulated in MeHg exposed animals. Reactive oxygen species were extremely high in pancreatic islets of MeHg treated groups. MeHg disrupted gluconeogenesis/glycogenolysis pathways and insulin secretory functions of islets by targeting GDH, GLUT2 and GCK genes of pancreatic islets. In conclusion, the current study revealed that insulin pathways, oxidative balance and glucose metabolism encoded genetic makeup are susceptible to MeHg toxicity and the subsequent oxidative stress and alter-

nations in gene expression could lead toward functional abnormalities in other organs.”; author: {“dropping-part icle”:””, “family”:”Maqbool”, “given”:”Faheem”, “non-dropping-part icle”:””, “parse-names”:false, “suffix”:””}; {“dropping-part icle”:””, “family”:”Bahadar”, “given”:”Haji”, “non-dropping-part icle”:””, “parse-names”:false, “suffix”:””}; {“dr opping-part icle”:””, “family”:”Niaz”, “given”:”Kamal”, “non-dropping-part icle”:””, “parse-names”:false, “suffix”:””}; {“dropping-part icle”:””, “family”:”Baeeri”, “given”:”Maryam”, “non-dropping-part icle”:””, “parse-names”:false, “suffi x”:””}; {“dropping-part icle”:””, “family”:”Rahimifard”, “give n”:”Mahban”, “non-dropping-part icle”:””, “parse-names”- :false, “suffix”:””}; {“dropping-part icle”:””, “family”:”Navaei- N i g j e h ””, “g i v e n ”:”M o n a ””, “n o n - d r o p p i n g - p a r t i c l e ”:””, “p a r s e - n a m e s ”:f a l s e, “s u f f i x ”:””}; {“dropping- p a r t i c l e ”:””, “f a m i l y ”:”G h a s e m i - N i r i ””, “g i v e n ”:”S e y e d e h F a r n a z ””, “n o n - d r o p p i n g - p a r t i c l e ”:””, “p a r s e - n a m e s ”:f a l s e, “s u f f i x ”:””}; {“dropping-part icle”:””, “family”:”Abdollahi”, “g i v e n ”:”M o h a m m a d ””, “n o n - d r o p p i n g - p a r t i c l e ”:””, “p a r s e - n a m e s ”:f a l s e, “s u f f i x ”:””}; “container-title”:”Food and Chemical Toxicology”, “id”:”ITEM-1”, “issued”: {“date- p a r t s ”:[[“2016”]]}, “page”:”119-128”, “publisher”:”Else- v i e r L t d ””, “t i t l e ”:”E f f e c t s o f m e t h y l m e r c u r y o n t h e a c t i v i t y a n d g e n e e x p r e s s i o n o f m o u s e L a n g e r h a n s i s - l e t s a n d g l u c o s e m e t a b o l i s m ””, “t y p e ”:”a r t i c l e - j o u r n a l ””, “v o l u m e ”:”93”}, “uris”: [“http://www.mendeley.com/ d o c u m e n t s / ? u u i d = 2 c 0 6 d a 2 c - 8 8 5 1 - 4 d 0 a - a 0 1 5 - 5 5 2 c 7 4 9 9 5 6 a b ”]]}, “mendeley”: {“formattedCitation”:”<sup>37</su p>”, “plainTextFormattedCitation”:”37”, “previouslyFormat tedCitation”:”³⁷”, “properties”: {“noteIndex ”:0}, “schema”:”https://github.com/citation-style-language/ s c h e m a / r a w / m a s t e r / c s l - c i t a t i o n . j s o n ”}. The results of this study are also in line with the study of Chen et al. who found a marked increase in blood glucose levels after 2-4 weeks of exposure to low doses of mercury. Oral administration of HgCl_2 at a dose of 250 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kgBB}$ for 14 days also showed a significant effect on an increase in GDP levels of >7.0 mmol/L (prediabetes) accompanied by the involvement of oxidative stress as an important regulator of glucose homeostasis during mercury chloride exposure. The study by Benloughmari Douae et al. found that in the group exposed to HgCl_2 , rats were given 0.375 mg/kg/day of HgCl_2 orally for 45 consecutive days showing a significant improvement in fasting blood glu- cose levels compared to the control group ($p < 0.001$)³⁸ with a range of mental health disorders including such as anxiety and depression. Whereas, mercury chloride (HgCl_2).

Methylmercury can negatively impact the development and function of pancreatic beta cells, potentially leading to reduced insulin production and increased insulin resistance and leading to increased fasting blood sugar levels.^{39,40} Hyperglycemic can also be induced by mercury due to beta cell RE stress, a study conducted by Placido Rojas-Francoa et al. showed that HgCl_2 activates PERK, ATF-4, ATF-6, and IRE1 which are sensor proteins that activate UPR during ER stress.²⁶ Likewise, research conducted by Wei Liu et al. found that methyl-

mercury causes oxidative stress, apoptosis, increased expression of GRP78, GRP94, Xbp1, ATF4, ER kinase-elf2a, inositol, and ATF6, as well as EBP and caspase-12 proteins.²⁷ which induces severe toxic effects in central nervous system. Oxidative stress is involved in various ways of intracellular physiological or pathological processes including neuronal apoptosis. For understanding the ways that oxidative stress participating in MeHg-induced apoptosis, the current study attempted to explore the effects of oxidative stress on endoplasmic reticulum (ER) The results of the above study are in line with the results of this study, namely the presence of hyperglycemic events directly or indirectly related to the occurrence of RE stress known from the markers of RE stress (increased expression of GRP 78 and JNKp and decrease in the number of Ca²⁺ ions).

Conclusions

The study found that mercury exposure causes hyperglycemic due to EE stress of pancreatic beta cells characterized by depletion intracellular Ca²⁺ and increased JNKp dan GRP78. This found can make a new approach in understanding the pathophysiology of mercury-induced defects in pancreatic beta cells and opens up the opportunity to find the right diabetes mellitus therapy induced by mercury.

Conflict of interests . None

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